

THE CONTENT AND FEATURES OF ACTIVITIES TO CREATE A NEW PRODUCT

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

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Abstract. This article discusses the methods of studying a new product, marketing a product, a marketing program, researching the opinions of consumers, distributors, etc. in order to determine the degree of compliance of a product with consumer needs.

Keywords: enterprise, consumers, specialists, production, product, category, brand, design, packaging.

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПО СОЗДАНИЮ НОВОГО ПРОДУКТА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются методы изучения нового товара, маркетинг товара, маркетинговая программа, исследования мнений потребителей, дистрибьюторов и т.д. с целью определения степени соответствия товара запросам потребителей.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, потребители, специалисты, производство, товар, категория, бренд, дизайн, упаковка.

INTRODUCTION

Generally, the category of new includes fundamentally new, improved or modified goods. The latter category also includes products with improved design, more attractive packaging and a new brand. In addition, new products include existing products offered for sale in new markets.

Especially important is the release of new products for highly competitive markets, where it is very difficult to achieve a competitive advantage in any other way.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Methods for studying a new product include both conducting surveys (of consumers and specialists involved in the development, production and marketing of new products) and setting up special experiments.

Predictive information about the possible market fate of a new product can also be obtained on the basis of an analysis of the volume of sales (say, by studying life cycle curves) of similar products, from an analysis of the situation in the field of competition.

We specify the content of marketing research in relation to the individual stages of the development of a new product (product).

New product development - development of original products, product improvement and modernization, creation of new product brands through the organization's own R&D. Usually, the process of developing a new product is divided into several stages: idea generation, selection (selection) of ideas, development of a new product concept, its verification, development of a marketing strategy, analysis of business prospects, development of the product itself, test marketing and commercial production. For the effective implementation of work at these stages, it is necessary to conduct appropriate marketing research at some of them.

So, at the stage of generating ideas for a new product, surveys are conducted (consumers, employees of R&D departments, marketing, service and other services of the enterprise itself, employees of trade organizations, individual experts). Important information about the directions

for improving manufactured goods can be obtained from the study of complaints, complaints, typical causes of failures and repairs. The collection of secondary information (patents, research institute reports, etc.) can be essential. Often ideas about new products can be obtained at exhibitions and fairs.

Ideas for new products are best presented in a format convenient for their analysis. When compiling the rating of new ideas, such information is used based on the results of marketing research, such as the degree of satisfaction of consumer needs, market capacity, competitive conditions, estimated prices and distribution channels, etc.

When developing the concept of a new product, i.e. determining in which specific product the selected idea materializes, it is determined with which other products it will compete, and the positioning of the new product is carried out. The results of marketing research should also be widely used here.

The development of a marketing strategy is unthinkable without the use of a variety of marketing information for an estimated and forecast plan, including information obtained at earlier stages of developing a new product. Additionally, recommendations are given on the choice of strategies in the context of individual elements of the marketing mix; for this, the results of marketing research in the field of pricing, distribution channels, and product promotion can be used.

Business prospects analysis - Evaluation for a new product of the expected sales volume, costs and profits for their alignment with the goals of the organization. In other words, we are talking about assessing the attractiveness for the organization of a particular new product. Since in the case under consideration we are talking about predominantly predictive estimates, the forecasting methods considered earlier in one of the articles in a series of these publications are widely used.

One of the final stages of creating a new product is test marketing or market testing. Trial marketing is the testing of a product and marketing program under real market conditions. The purpose of test marketing is to evaluate the product itself and its marketing program (price, advertising, brand, packaging, service, etc.) even before the start of a full-scale implementation of the product, and find out how consumers and intermediaries will react to all this. The results of test marketing can be used to predict sales and profits. In trial marketing of consumer products, the following methods are used: standard market testing; control testing of the market; market simulation testing.

Standard market testing - market testing in which a new product is placed under conditions similar to those of a full-scale product release. Find specific outlets for the product where the organization's marketers conduct a complete marketing program, analyze store operations, conduct consumer, distributor, and other opinion surveys to determine the degree to which the product meets consumer needs. The purpose of routine testing is to use the results obtained to predict national sales and identify problems associated with the production and marketing of a given product.

Market benchmark testing is the creation of special panels of stores that agree to test different methods of selling a product for a fee. The organization that carries out control testing of the market, in accordance with its plans, determines the number and geographical location of stores, controls the location of the product on the trading floor, prices, and the chosen methods of promoting the product.

RESULTS

Analysis of the obtained results makes it possible to determine their impact on demand.

Simulation testing of the market - testing a product under conditions that simulate real conditions, for example, the purchase by consumers selected by the organization for the limited money allocated to them of goods, among which there is a new product, in a regular store or in a laboratory store of this organization. In this case, consumers are presented with samples of advertising and other methods of promoting various products, including the product being tested.

In trial marketing of production and technical purposes, product samples are transferred for a limited time for testing to potential customers. In addition, the product can be tested at exhibitions and demonstrations organized by trade, distributors and dealers.

From these data, it follows that developers of new products should first of all study the demographic, psychological, economic and other characteristics of superinnovators and innovators, first of all, since they are the ones who respond to new products in the first place. It is usually extremely difficult to do this, since the same people can behave differently with respect to different products, either being, say, innovators or conservatives.

Obviously, the success of new product development is greatly influenced by the external business environment, which also needs to be investigated.

Further, the content of marketing research of a new product is considered in two aspects: the study of the success factors of a new product and the determination of directions for the development of manufactured product models (using the example of new models of cars and trucks and the choice of options for providing medical services to the population). Thus, three main types of products will be covered: consumer goods, industrial products and services.

Organizations that are leaders in the development of new products usually devote a lot of attention to identifying the factors of their success, conducting special studies in this area.

The concretization of general success factors is usually carried out in the direction of obtaining quantitative estimates characterizing their relative role. The necessary information is primarily collected by experts both among the organization's employees (in the new technology department, in the R&D department, in the marketing and sales department, etc.), and among resellers and consumers.

DISCUSSION

Every firm, no matter what it produces - actually goods, services, information - should strive to create goods of market novelty, because only they can serve as the material basis for the successful existence of the company in the future. At the heart of the appearance of such products on the market are ideas. There are three types of marketing ideas for the formation of a product of market novelty:

- design, inventive ideas;
- design ideas;
- packaging ideas.

As for design and inventive ideas, everything here seems so simple, obvious and transparent that there is nothing to talk about: there was no product with certain design characteristics, and now it has finally appeared. Everyone sees its advantages, everyone wants to buy it, even those who have previous models of such a product, because the new model, being a

product of market novelty, in a different way, at a higher consumer level, solves the previous problems of buyers.

The objectively determined desire of people to replace a thing that is still usable for a new one, with more developed consumer properties, determines the rapid growth in the number of sales of market novelty goods, while they are still such.

Often, new consumer properties of a particular product, making it a product of market novelty, can be given to it through the embodiment of design ideas. After all, the design is designed to provide not only the sophistication of forms, the beauty of the product, but also the convenience of practical application.

The designer proposes a form that will provide the greatest increase in the number of sales of this product on the market, the designer-inventor must place the functional blocks of the product in this form.

Often, when developing market novelty products, the ideas of inventors and designers are used together, complementing each other and giving the product not only a complex of useful qualities (consumer properties), but also an exquisite appearance. Working together, these ideas provide the company with high sales during the period of market novelty of the product and its high stable level at the end of this period.

There are many examples of the successful application of design ideas in the design of market novelty products, both with and without the ideas of the inventors. They play an important role in the production of products that meet the conscious and unconscious expectations of customers.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, the quality of the product is formed both by the functional features of this product, the development of which is the prerogative of designers and technologists, and by the external design, in the development of which the marketer must take an obligatory part. The most important means used in product development and embodying the appearance of the product: the shape, color and material of the product.

Product shape is associated with both basic and additional qualities. Of the additional qualities, the most important is the aesthetics of the product. Physiological theory states that the image that is comfortable to the eye and covered by a small number of movements is the most aesthetic. Forms should consist of simple, consistent, as symmetrical lines and elements as possible.

The last kind of idea that underlies the formation of a market novelty product is packaging, which can turn a traditional product into a market novelty product. Until recently, it was believed that packaging should only perform the function of preserving the goods, be durable, convenient for transportation, and nothing more. However, in market conditions, packaging can and should perform other functions. One of these features is advertising. It is argued that the most effective advertising is advertising on the package. It really is.

Let us single out the key factors in the creation of packages that should be taken into account when making decisions in this direction.

1) *Package design* should influence the image that the company is looking for for its products. Color, shape, materials - all this affects the perception of consumers about the

company and its products. Plainer packaging creates an image of lower quality for generic brands.

2) *Standardization* packaging increases global recognition. For this reason, Pepsi-Cola and Coca-Cola use the same packaging in all parts of the world.

3) *Packaging cost* must of course be taken into account. The relative cost of packaging can reach up to 40% of the retail price, depending on the purpose and degree of packaging.

4) *Modern materials* stimulate demand. A firm can choose from a range of packaging materials: cardboard, plastic, metal, glass, cellophane, etc. Compromises are sometimes necessary. For example, cellophane allows products to be displayed, but it tears very easily; cardboard is relatively cheap but difficult to open. In addition, you need to determine how innovative the packaging should be.

5) Then the firm must choose the size, color and shape. When choosing sizes, you need to consider the period of storage, convenience, tradition and competition. The location, content and size of the label, as well as how prominent it should be, must also be specified. The name of the company and the brand of the product should be indicated on it.

Multiple packaging combines two or more units of goods.

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